

Halal Tourism in West Java: Behavior and Preferences of Non-Muslims Based on TPB Theory in Indonesia

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Abstract:

Research Objectives:

This study aims to investigate the behavior and preferences of non-Muslim tourists towards halal tourism offerings in West Java using the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as a theoretical framework. The objectives include understanding the attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influencing non-Muslim tourists' intentions and behaviors related to halal tourism in the region.

Methodology:

A sample of 116 non-Muslim respondents will be surveyed to assess their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control towards halal tourism in West Java. Data will be analyzed using SPSS 20.0 and Smart-PLS 3.0 software to evaluate the relationships between these variables and non-Muslim tourists' intentions and behaviors towards halal tourism offerings.

Finding:

The study will analyze the data to determine the impact of Halal Tourism's subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and Attitude on non-Muslim tourists' preferences and behaviors regarding Halal tourism in West Java. As a result, Halal Tourism's subjective norms do not affect Halal Tourism Visit Intention, while Halal Tourism's subjective norms and attitudes affect Halal Tourism's visit intention.

Practical Implications:

The findings of this research will offer valuable insights for tourism stakeholders and destination managers in West Java to tailor their offerings to better cater to the needs and preferences of non-Muslim tourists. By understanding the factors that drive non-Muslim tourists' intentions and behaviors towards halal tourism, stakeholders can enhance the overall tourism experience for this segment of visitors, ultimately contributing to developing more inclusive and appealing halal tourism products in West Java.

Originality:

The novelty of this research lies in several aspects, namely: New focus: Most similar research focuses on Muslim tourists. This research shifts to a non-Muslim perspective.

West Java was chosen as a case study location because of its significant potential in halal tourism, although there is still minimal research. This study will explore how non-Muslim tourists respond to the integration of cultural and Islamic religious elements in halal tourism.

Motivational factors: This research will identify the elements that encourage non-Muslim tourists to choose halal tourist destinations.

Keywords: Halal tourism subjective norms, halal tourism perceived behavioral control, halal tourism attitude, halal tourism visit intention, non-muslim, west Java.

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Introduction

Halal tourism is a growing idea that has received considerable focus in recent years, especially in Muslim-majority nations such as Indonesia (Wang, 2019; Juliana et al., 2023a). This study examines the conduct and inclinations of non-Muslim Javanese citizens in West Java (Ratnasari et al., 2021), explicitly emphasizing how their attitude towards halal tourism affects their desire to engage in halal tourism activities (Kastenholz et al., 2018).

Halal tourism in West Java has attracted considerable attention because it could increase Indonesia's status as a leading destination (Juliana et al., 2022). Various studies have investigated various aspects of halal tourism, including the behavior and preferences of non-Muslims towards destinations. Studies have used the theory of planned behavior (TPB) to understand what influences customer behavior and recommendation intentions in the halal tourism industry (Abbasi et al., 2021). The intention to propose elements in the halal tourism experience has been examined using this theoretical framework.

Additionally, this research has focused on the development of halal tourism in West Java to find problems and offer solutions to maintain growth. According to Huda and colleagues, by 2020, this region can become the center of Indonesian halal tourism and emphasizes increasing income through tourism (D. Ratnasari et al., 2023; Juliana et al., 2023b). In addition, research has been conducted on how Indonesian intellectual thought contributes to the development of halal tourism in the country, demonstrating the role of local intellectuals in this sector (Rahman et al., 2020). Research on the relationship between Islamic banks and Muslim-friendly tourism companies to create new strategies to drive the halal industry in Indonesia has been conducted (Adinugraha et al., 2021). Further research has also been conducted on the impact of halal destination awareness on visitor loyalty (Takhim et al., 2023). This suggests that greater attention is being directed towards developing Muslim-friendly tourism (Safira & Salsabilia, 2022). In addition, efforts by Islamic human resources to support the growth of halal tourism in West Java have been studied, emphasizing the tourism industry's economic prospects (Joeliaty et al., 2021).

Studies have examined how important halal tourism is for Indonesian Muslim tourists when traveling to non-Muslim places, emphasizing their unique needs and perceptions (Wibawa et al., 2023; Juliana et al., 2024a). Additionally, studies have examined how tourists' perceptions of halal products and services impact their loyalty to halal tourism destinations, emphasizing how perceptions influence their behavior (M. Rahman et al., 2020).

Literature Review

Theory of Planned Behavior

In the recent years, the concept of halal tourism has gained significant attention globally (Juliana, et al., 2024). Many nations, both in the Islamic world and beyond, have recognized the potential of the Muslim travel market and have started to capitalize on the rising demand for Muslim-friendly tourist services (Sánchez & Moral, 2019; Yan et al., 2017). Halal tourism refers to products, recreation, leisure, and social activities that comply with Islamic teachings or Muslim-friendly principles (Rahman et al., 2020).

Henderson argues that the concept of Islamic tourism is a relatively recent phenomenon, despite the significance attached to travel in

Islam (Sánchez & Moral, 2019). However, Elaziz and Kurt signal that "modern day tourism practices emanate from hedonistic intentions, which are not present in the Islamic faith," suggesting that the terminology of "halal tourism" is more of a brand name than an actual religious practice.

In this study, we used The Theory of Planned Behavior, explains that an individual's attitude towards a behavior is a key factor that can be used to predict the action. However, it is also necessary to consider subjective norms and the measurement of perception of one's behavioral control in testing a behavior. Planned behavior theory involves three independent variables. The first is attitude towards behavior, where a person evaluates the advantages and disadvantages of an action. The second is a social factor called subjective norm, which refers to the perceived social pressure to carry out or not carry out an action. Third, there is an intention that reflects the perception of behavior control, including the extent to which a person feels that doing or not doing the behavior is easy or difficult, as well as anticipating obstacles based on past experience (Ajzen, 1991).

Subjective Norms in Halal Tourism

Subjective norms are influential factors in shaping individuals' intentions and behaviors within halal tourism. Research consistently demonstrates subjective norms' positive and significant impact on the intention to visit halal tourist areas (Abbasi et al., 2021). Particularly within the context of Muslim diaspora tourists, a halal subjective norm is defined as a social pressure that promotes engagement in halal behavior (Mohammed et al., 2022). This social influence extends to consumer intentions to visit cities with halal tourism concepts, underscoring the role of subjective norms in travel decision-making (Julina & Kariyawan, 2020).

Furthermore, subjective norms are crucial in adopting halal tourism concepts within the hospitality and tourism industries. The perceived benefits of halal tourism are vital for the competitiveness of businesses operating in this sector (Mohamed et al., 2022). Additionally, religiosity has been found to mediate the relationship between subjective norms, attitudes, perceived behavioral control, and the intention to visit halal tourism areas (Julina et al., 2021).

Moreover, studies have shown that subjective norms significantly impact consumers' intentions to purchase halal food products. Regardless of their level of Islamic religiosity, subjective norms emerge as the most influential determinant of the intention to buy food products labeled as halal (Maulina et al., 2021). Similarly, in halal food consumption, subjective norms play a significant role in shaping the intention to purchase halal products (Harun et al., 2023).

In the development of halal tourism, subjective norms are linked to meeting the needs of Muslim tourists, particularly in providing facilities and services that align with Islamic principles (Purusottama & Prastowo, 2019). The influence of subjective norms on consumer interest in halal-certified restaurants further highlights the importance of social pressures in influencing behaviors within the halal tourism sector (Cahyaningsih & Nugroho, 2022).

In conclusion, subjective norms are pivotal in shaping consumer behaviors and intentions in halal tourism. Understanding the impact of social pressures and normative influences is crucial for devising strategies that cater to the needs and preferences of individuals participating in halal tourism experiences.

Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC)

Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC) is a crucial component of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) that significantly influences individuals' intentions and behaviors. PBC is defined as individuals' beliefs regarding their ability to perform a behavior and their perceived level of control over it (Ajzen, 2002). Recent studies have indicated that PBC comprises two main elements: self-efficacy, which focuses on the ease or difficulty of performing a behavior, and controllability, which refers to the degree of control an individual has over the behavior (Ajzen, 2002).

Research has consistently shown that PBC is vital in predicting and explaining behaviors that may not be entirely within an individual's volitional control (Hall & Zehr, 2016). Incorporating PBC into the TPB has enhanced the model's predictive capacity, particularly for behaviors influenced by factors beyond individual control (Hall & Zehr, 2016). Furthermore, empirical evidence suggests that PBC is a crucial determinant of intention and behavior, independently of other variables in the TPB (Armitage & Conner, 2001).

Moreover, numerous studies have identified PBC as a significant predictor of various behaviors, such as strength training in older adults and engagement in physical activities among the elderly (Alexandris et al., 2007; Dean et al., 2007). Individuals' perceived resources and constraints directly impact their PBC, subsequently influencing their intentions and behaviors (Alexandris et al., 2007). Additionally, PBC has been recognized as a critical factor in predicting behaviors related to seeking psychological help and blood donation (Aras & Peker, 2024; Armitage & Conner, 2001).

In conclusion, PBC is a fundamental element of the TPB, shaping individuals' intentions and behaviors by reflecting their beliefs about their control over executing a specific behavior. A comprehensive understanding of the role of PBC is essential for effectively predicting and elucidating a wide array of behaviors across diverse contexts.

Halal Tourism Attitude Concept

The concept of attitudes towards halal tourism significantly shapes individuals' perceptions and behaviors within Islamic tourism. Studies have explored the importance of positive attitudes towards halal tourism destinations in influencing tourists' intentions to visit and engage with halal offerings (M. Rahman et al., 2020). The development of favorable attitudes towards halal tourism is crucial for promoting the growth and sustainability of this niche market within the broader tourism industry.

Furthermore, the literature emphasizes the essential pillars of halal tourism, including non-alcoholic drinks, halal food, gender segregation, provision of prayer facilities, restrictions on women traveling alone, and adherence to modest dress codes (Nakyinsige et al., 2012). These pillars reflect the fundamental principles of halal tourism and contribute to shaping tourists' attitudes towards destinations that align with Islamic values and practices.

Moreover, there is a growing recognition of the need to address misunderstandings and misconceptions surrounding halal tourism, particularly in destinations like Bandung, Indonesia (Wahyudin et al., 2022). Clarifying the concept of halal tourism and highlighting its alignment with Islamic teachings can help enhance tourists' attitudes towards halal offerings and promote a deeper understanding of the principles underpinning this form of tourism.

Additionally, the literature underscores the significance of place attachment and the value-belief-norm theory in shaping attitudes toward halal tourism development (D. Ratnasari et al., 2023). By fostering a sense of attachment to destinations that offer halal services and experiences, stakeholders can cultivate positive attitudes among tourists and enhance their overall satisfaction with halal tourism offerings.

Furthermore, research has explored the impact of tourists' perceptions of halal tourism destinations, highlighting the role of attitudes in influencing visitors' intentions and behaviors (Maesaroh et al., 2024). Understanding tourists' attitudes towards halal tourism destinations is essential for destination marketers to tailor their offerings and communication strategies effectively.

In conclusion, the literature on the attitude concept in halal tourism underscores the importance of fostering positive attitudes, addressing misconceptions, and promoting destination attachment to enhance tourists' experiences and engagement with halal tourism offerings. By cultivating favorable attitudes towards halal tourism, destinations can attract and retain visitors seeking authentic and culturally sensitive travel experiences.

Halal Tourism Visit Intention Concept

Ajzen & Fishbein (1991) argues that intention (interest) is an internal element in a person that reflects the desire to perform a particular action or behavior. This intention is described as a subjective dimension regarding the extent to which individuals feel that the action or behavior is beneficial to them. Intention in behavior can be described in several aspects, such as goals, actions, situations, and timing (Suhud et al., 2024). Intention refers to the probability of a person carrying out a particular action. The concept of premeditated behavior theory states that there are several key assumptions that need to be considered in the sense of intention. First, intention functions as an intermediary that influences an individual's motivation towards certain behaviors. Second, intention describes the extent to which a person is committed to trying or carrying out the action. Third, intention also reflects the level of effort that the individual gives to realize his plan in carrying out the special behavior. (Afrianty, 2021). The perception and intention of tourists, both Muslim and non-Muslim, toward halal tourism destinations play a crucial role in the development of this burgeoning industry.

Method

The research method used in this study is quantitative with descriptive and causalitas research design. The data collection technique used in this study is by using a questionnaire, which is a data collection technique by collecting questions and distributing them to the research respondents. The respondents in this study are Non Muslim tourists who have never visited and intend to visit halal tourism in West Java. This questionnaire will be shared via google form via *WhatsAppGroup and Telegram*. Data was collected using the Numerical scale of 116 non-Muslim domestic tourists in Indonesia between July and August 2024. The sample size meets the minimum requirements based on the research model of Hair et al. (2019). Sampling was carried out using the convenience sampling method.

This study uses a Numerical scale with scores ranging from 1 to 7 to assess variables. The measuring instrument is adapted from

previous research: Halal Tourism Subjective Norm (HT-SN) by (Ajzen, 2002; Aziz & Chok, 2013 Iranmanesh et al., 2020; Jae-Jang et al., 2020); Halal Tourism Perceived Behavioral Control (HT-PBC) by (Ajzen, 2002; Iranmanesh et al., 2020; Preston & Post, 2012), Halal Tourism Attitude (HT-ATT) by (Iranmanesh et al., 2020; Jae-Jang et al., 2020; M. et al. et al., 2015), and Halal Tourism Visit Intention (HT-VINT) by (Ajzen, 2002; Aziz & Chok, 2013; Japutra et al., 2021; Preston & Post, 2012).

The data analysis in this study uses the Partial Least Square-Based Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach with the WarpPLS 5.0 program. The researchers chose the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) approach due to several factors. First, PLS-SEM has been recognized for handling small sample sizes effectively, as highlighted by (Chin, 1998). Second, in the specific context of small samples, PLS-SEM has shown its potential to produce more robust statistical analysis results than CB SEM, as emphasized by (Hair et al., 2013).

Results and Discussion

Test Instrument

Based on the described stages achieved, the following are data processing results for validity and reliability testing. Validity testing is needed to determine whether the instrument used to search for primary data in a study can be used to measure what should be measured. In this study, the validity of the variable instruments Halal Tourism Subjective Norm (HT-SN), Halal Tourism Perceived Behavioral Control (HT-PB), Halal Tourism Attitude (HT-AT), and Halal Tourism Visit Intention (HT-VI) will be tested. The number of statements for the HT-SN variable was five items, the HT-PB variable was five items, the HT-AT variable was six items, and the HT-VI variable was four. The number of questionnaires tested was 37 respondents with a significance level of 0.05 and degrees of freedom (dk) = n - 2 (37 - 2 = 35), and then a table of 0.235 was obtained.

Table 1. Instrument Test Result

Halal Tourism Subjective Norm (HT-SN)				
Item	Statement	r-value	r-table	Description
HT-SN1	My family thinks that I should try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.981	0.325	Valid
HT-SN2	People I respect think that I should try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.985	0.325	Valid
HT-SN3	A close friend of mine thinks that I should try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.986	0.325	Valid
Item	Statement	r-value	r-table	Description
HT-SN4	I am expected to try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.979	0.325	Valid
HT-SN5	Many people like me visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.953	0.325	Valid
Cronbach's Alpha HT-SN		0.993		Reliable
Halal Tourism Perceived Behavioral Control (HT-PB)				
Item	Statement	r-value	r-table	Description
HT-PB1	If I want to, I will try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.794	0.325	Valid
HT-PB2	I think it is easy for me to try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.769	0.325	Valid
HT-PB3	For me, trying to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism) is a possible thing	0.741	0.325	Valid
HT-PB4	I have the resources and opportunities (e.g., money, time) to try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.787	0.325	Valid
HT-PB5	I have full control in deciding to try to visit halal tourist destinations (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.442	0.325	Valid
Cronbach's Alpha HT-PB		0.786		Reliable
Halal Tourism Attitude (HT-AT)				
Item	Statement	r-value	r-table	Description
HT-AT1	Halal tourism products (Muslim-friendly tourism) are important	0.935	0.325	Valid
HT-AT2	Halal tourism services (Muslim-friendly tourism) are important	0.908	0.325	Valid
HT-AT3	Trying to choose a halal tourist destination (Muslim-friendly tourism) is a good idea	0.920	0.325	Valid

HT-AT4	Trying to choose a halal tourist destination (Muslim-friendly tourism) is fun	0.956	0.325	Valid
HT-AT5	Trying to choose a halal tourist destination (Muslim-friendly tourism) is interesting	0.957	0.325	Valid
HT-AT6	I try to choose tourist destinations that have halal tourism facilities (Muslim-friendly tourism)	0.973	0.325	Valid
Cronbach's Alpha HT-AT		0.946		Reliable
Halal Tourism Visit Intention (HT-VI)				
Item	Statement	r-value	r-table	Description
HT-VI1	I am willing to try to visit halal tourist destinations	0.935	0.325	Valid
HT-VI2	I plan to try to visit halal tourist destinations in the coming days	0.908	0.325	Valid
HT-VI3	I would recommend the destination as a halal tourist destination	0.956	0.325	Valid
HT-VI4	I intend to recommend the halal tourist destination to others	0.957	0.325	Valid
Cronbach's Alpha HT-VI		0.946		Reliable

Source: Data processed with SPSS 23

The validity test results, conducted using the IBM SPSS program version 25.0 for Windows (Table 1), demonstrated that all statement items within the questionnaire are considered valid. This is evidenced by the r-calculated values exceeding the r-table threshold of 0.325. Consequently, all the information provided through these statements is deemed accurate, ensuring that the questionnaire is a valid research instrument for effectively measuring the variables related to halal tourism visit intention. This validation confirms that the data collected can reliably support further analysis and interpretation within the scope of the study.

Reliability testing is then carried out to show the extent to which the data is error-free to ensure consistent measurements throughout the instrument. The instrument's reliability test results with IBM SPSS version 25.0 for Windows (Table 1) show that all variables are reliable because the value of Cronbach's alpha in each variable is more significant than 0.6.

Table 2. Respondent Profile

	Total	Percentage
Gender		
Female	65	60%
Male	43	40%
The Domisili		
Sumatera	66	62%
Jawa	28	26%
Sulawesi	7	6%
Bali dan Nusa Tenggara	6	5%
Kalimantan	1	1%
Occupation		
Private Employee	40	37%
Student/Students	23	21%
Civil Servant	19	18%
Entrepreneurial	15	14%
Other	11	10%
Income		
<3M per month	34	32%
>8 million per month	26	24%
3 to 5 million per month	24	22%
5 to 8 million per month	24	22%

Descriptive Analysis

The description of the research variables aims to provide an overview of the respondents' responses or answers to previously filled-out questionnaires through Google Forms. To determine the category of an answer, whether it is classified as very high, high, relatively high, quite low, low, or very low. The indicators in the variables Halal Tourism Subjective Norm (HT-SN), Halal Tourism Perceived Behavioral Control (HT-PB), Halal Tourism Attitude (HT-AT), and Halal Tourism Visit Intention (HT-VI) have mean values in the high category (Table 3).

Table 3. Descriptive Analysis and Factor Charge

Halal Tourism Subjective Norm (HT-SN)				
Item	Mean	Factor Loading	P Value	Ket. Mean
HT-SN1	5,2	0,922	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-SN2	5,3	0,938	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-SN3	5,2	0,936	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-SN4	5,4	0,919	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-SN5	5,4	0,802	<0.001	Tinggi
Halal Tourism Perceived Behavioral Control (HT-PB)				
Item	Mean	Factor Loading	P Value	Ket. Mean
HT-PB1	5,7	0,849	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-PB2	5,4	0,871	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-PB3	5,5	0,863	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-PB4	5,6	0,852	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-PB5	5,7	0,708	<0.001	Tinggi
Halal Tourism Attitude (HT-AT)				
Item	Mean	Factor Loading	P Value	Ket. Mean
HT-AT1	5,3	0,867	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-AT2	5,4	0,882	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-AT3	5,4	0,880	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-AT4	5,3	0,924	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-AT5	5,3	0,908	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-AT6	5,2	0,878	<0.001	Tinggi
Halal Tourism Visit Intention (HT-VI)				
Item	Mean	Factor Loading	P Value	Ket. Mean
HT-VI1	5,6	0,905	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-VI2	5,3	0,875	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-VI3	5,4	0,903	<0.001	Tinggi
HT-VI4	5,6	0,940	<0.001	Tinggi

Source: Data processed with SPSS 23 and WarpPLS 5.0

Measurement Model Evaluation

Based on Table 3, if an indicator's loading factor value is more significant than 0.7 or its P-value value is lower than 0.05, then the indicator can be used, but those that do not meet these criteria are not used. The convergent validity conditions have been met based on each indicator's factor loading and P-value values.

Tabel 4. Fronell-Larcker Criterion

	HT-SN	HT-PB	HT-AT	HT-IV
HT-SN	0,905			
HT-PB	0,684	0,831		
HT-AT	0,745	0,783	0,890	
HT-IV	0,708	0,820	0,745	0,906

Source: Data diolah dengan WarpPLS 5.0

Furthermore, to test the validity of discrimination, the Fornell-Larcker criterion compares the square root of the AVE with the correlation between latent variables. In particular, the square root of each AVE must be greater than its highest correlation with the other constructs, given that, in statistical terms, a latent variable has more variance to its indicators than any other latent variable. Table 4 shows that the square root value of AVE in each variable (bold value) is greater than the correlation between latent variables, which shows the fulfillment of the validity of discrimination.

Table 5. Model Reliability Test and Collinearity

	HT-SN	HT-PB	HT-AT	HT-IV
Composite reliability	0,957	0,917	0,958	0,948
Cronbach's alpha	0,944	0,886	0,947	0,927
VIF	2,418	3,410	4,521	4,789

Source: Data processed with WarpPLS 5.0

Furthermore, Table 5 shows that the composite and Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients are more significant than 0.7 for each variable. The composite reliability coefficient and Cronbach's alpha value of each variable determine whether or not the composite reliability requirements and internal consistency reliability are met. If the requirements of convergent validity, discriminatory validity, composite reliability, and internal consistency reliability are met, then the outer model requirements have been met.

Table 5 also shows that each variable's VIF value is less than 5. Thus, there is no indication of collinearity, and the statistical assumption of SEM-PLS can be met.

Table 6. Model Fit

	Value	Minimum Value	Description
Average path coefficient (APC)	P-value < 0,001	P-value<0,05	Good Fit
Average R-squared (ARS)	P-value < 0,001	P-value<0,05	Good Fit
Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)	P-value < 0,001	P-value<0,05	Good Fit
Average block VIF (AVIF)	2,883	Value<=5	Good Fit
Average full collinearity (AFVIF)	3,785	Value<=5	Good Fit
Sympson's paradox Ratio (SPR)	1,000	Value>=0,7	Good Fit
R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)	1,000	Value>=0,9	Good Fit
Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)	1,000	Value>=0,7	Good Fit
Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)	1,000	Value>=0,7	Good Fit

Source: Data processed with WarpPLS 5.0

Table 6 shows that the model meets the fit model criteria. Based on this, the fit model's requirements are met, and the fulfillment of the fit model's requirements meets the inner model's requirements.

Structural Model Evaluation

The outer model and inner model have been evaluated thoroughly. Furthermore, a hypothesis test was carried out with the WarpPLS program, where the analysis was explained as follows:

Table 7. Uji Hipotesis

Correlation	Beta	P-Value	Keterangan
HT-SN → HT-VI (H1)	0,107	0,127	Not Sig.
HT-PB → HT-VI (H2)	0,349	<0,001	Sig.
HT-AT → HT-VI (H3)	0,501	<0,001	Sig.
R-square		0,793	

Source: Data processed with WarpPLS 5.0

Table 7 above shows that Hypothesis 1 (H1) is insignificant or unproven, while Hypothesis 2 (H2) and Hypothesis 3 (H3) are significant or proven. For the R-square value, there is the following classification: R-square < 0.02 (weak), R-square > 0.15 (moderate), and R-square > 0.35 (strong). Based on this information, the predictive determination construction for this model is included in the strong category (R-square = 0.793). Based on comparing Beta values, the HT-AT → HT-VI pathways have the most considerable Beta value compared to the HT-PB → HT-VI pathways.

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Data processed with WarpPLS 5.0

Based on Figure 1's output, non-Muslim tourists' attitudes towards halal tourism can encourage their interest in visiting halal tourist destinations. In other words, the better their attitude towards halal tourism, the more interested they will be in visiting halal tourist destinations.

Discussion

The Impact of Subjective Norms on Halal Tourism Visit Intention

The increasing prevalence of halal tourism has generated considerable curiosity in comprehending the determinants that impact travelers' inclination to visit halal sites. One element that has been investigated is the influence of subjective norms, which are the perceived societal expectations to participate in a specific behavior. Nevertheless, this study discovered no statistically significant correlation between subjective norms and the intention to visit halal tourism sites, as indicated by a p-value of 0.127. These findings challenge prior research that has indicated a positive correlation between subjective norms and the desire to participate in halal-related behaviors, such as the intention to select halal products (Haziq et al., 2014).

Despite the prevailing literature indicating the significant influence of subjective norms on consumer behavior, particularly on halal products and services, this finding is somewhat unexpected. Prior research has demonstrated that subjective norms favorably impact customers' attitudes and intentions when selecting halal products. Furthermore, extensive research has consistently shown that the influence of friends and family members and subjective norms play a significant role in motivating individuals to buy halal personal care products.

Nevertheless, the correlation between subjective norms and the propensity to attend halal tourism seems intricate. An alternative

explanation for the lack of a significant relationship could be that the choice to visit a halal tourism destination is primarily influenced by other factors, such as the perceived excellence of the halal services and products available or the overall appeal of the destination to non-Muslim tourists (M. Rahman et al., 2020).

As emphasized in the literature, halal tourism extends beyond the mere supply of halal food and beverages, encompassing a diverse array of products and services that specifically cater to the requirements of Muslim travelers (Jae-Jang YANG & Sun-Choung AHN, 2020). Within this framework, elements such as the accessibility of prayer amenities, a socially favorable atmosphere, and the general adherence to Islamic principles may significantly impact tourists' intentions to visit.

Moreover, subjective norms may significantly impact the early phases of halal tourism development when the notion is still novel and unfamiliar to the broader travel market. As halal tourism gains popularity and acceptance, the impact of subjective norms may be overshadowed by other individual reasons when deciding whether to attend.

To summarise, the discovery of a negligible correlation between subjective norms and the intention to visit halal tourism destinations emphasizes the necessity for a more intricate comprehension of the elements that influence travelers' actions in this growing industry.

The Impact of Halal Tourism Perceived Behavior on Halal Tourism Visit Intention

Halal tourism, which specifically caters to the requirements and preferences of Muslim travelers, has garnered growing attention from professionals in business and scholars conducting research. Nevertheless, the significant influence of non-Muslim travelers' impressions on their inclination to visit halal tourism destinations has often been disregarded (Battour, 2018). In this study, Halal

Perceived Behaviors positively and significantly affects Halal Tourism Visit intention. The objective of this study is to examine the correlation between the perceived conduct of non-Muslim tourists and their inclination to visit halal tourism places. A recent study indicates that introducing halal food services and prohibiting non-halal services significantly impact non-Muslim travelers' trip experience and value (M. Rahman et al., 2020). These factors, in turn, affect their satisfaction and loyalty towards halal tourism destinations. Moreover, the study suggests that overall halal services have a favorable correlation with the value of the trip but not with the trip's experience. The research above emphasizes the significance of comprehending non-Muslim tourists' viewpoints and choices within halal tourism (M. Rahman et al., 2020). Non-Muslim travelers may be drawn to halal tourism locations because of the distinct cultural experiences and the presence of halal-certified services, such as halal food and prayer facilities. Nevertheless, the study indicates that non-Muslim travelers may harbor apprehensions regarding the possible constraints or constraints on specific activities or services that do not align with their cultural or personal inclinations.

In order to accommodate the requirements and desires of both Muslim and non-Muslim travelers, halal tourism sites and service providers should aim to find a harmonious middle ground between adhering to Islamic principles and meeting the varied needs of their clientele. Non-Muslim countries have observed the increasing interest in halal tourism, leading their governments and tourism authorities to understand better the idea of halal and the requirements of Muslim travelers. Nevertheless, the study highlights the significance of considering the reciprocal advantages for Muslim and non-Muslim passengers to guarantee the enduring viability of the halal tourism sector. Overall, this study offers a significant understanding of the viewpoints and choices of non-Muslim tourists about halal tourism. The results indicate that gaining a deeper comprehension of the behaviors and preferences of non-Muslim tourists will assist halal tourism locations and service providers in creating more comprehensive and attractive offerings. This, in turn, will contribute to the expansion and long-term viability of the halal tourism industry.

The Influence of Halal Tourism Attitude on Halal Tourism Visit Intention

The findings of this study suggest that non-Muslim Javanese citizens in West Java hold a favorable disposition towards halal tourism, which subsequently impacts their inclination to visit halal tourism locations. This discovery is consistent with the current body of research, which indicates that the growth of halal tourism can have a favorable influence on tourist attraction and visitation, even among non-Muslim communities (Abror et al., 2019; Gohary et al., 2020; Kastenholz et al., 2018; Wang, 2019). Multiple research studies have examined the viewpoints of non-Muslim travelers on halal tourism, emphasizing the significance of comprehending this growing phenomenon (Yan et al., 2017). The results indicate that non-Muslim tourists are generally open to halal tourism, particularly regarding halal cuisine and other services that cater to their requirements (M. Rahman et al., 2020).

The literature has investigated the influence of non-Muslim visitors' perceptions on their inclination to visit areas that are accommodating to halal practices. The findings suggest that the introduction of halal food services and the prohibition of non-halal

services have a notable beneficial effect on the travel experience and perceived worth for non-Muslims. This, in turn, affects their satisfaction and loyalty towards the location (M. Rahman et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Although halal tourism is associated with religious values, subjective norms (an individual's perception of the expectations of those closest to them about a halal tourism visit) are not significant to the intention to go. This suggests that a person's internal motivation dominates their decision to visit halal tourist attractions more than social pressure or environmental influences. People's perceived behavior of halal tourism significantly influences their intention to visit. The more positive their perception of halal tourism, the more likely they are to visit halal tourism destinations. This shows that people's understanding and beliefs about halal tourism are essential in driving their interest in visiting. Positive attitudes towards halal tourism also significantly affect visiting intentions; People who have a positive attitude towards halal tourism tend to be more interested in visiting halal tourist destinations. This shows that individual evaluation of halal tourism is essential in shaping visiting intentions. With the increasing popularity of halal tourism in West Java, it is imperative for tourism stakeholders to meticulously take into account the requirements and inclinations of both Muslim and non-Muslim guests. Destination managers can gain insights into non-Muslim guests' behaviors, attitudes, and concerns to foster a more inclusive and hospitable atmosphere accommodating all tourists' interests and backgrounds.

These findings have several practical implications for the development of halal tourism in West Java. The positive attitude towards halal tourism among non-Muslim Javanese individuals suggests that the industry can expand beyond the Muslim market, catering to a broader audience and diversifying its customer base. Additionally, the strong relationship between halal tourism attitude and visit intention highlights the importance of effectively promoting and marketing halal tourism offerings to this population segment.

To further explore this topic, future research could investigate the specific factors that shape the halal tourism attitudes and behaviors of non-Muslim Javanese individuals and the potential barriers or challenges they may face in engaging with halal tourism.

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